

VIRTUAL OPEN FORUM EVENT

Biobanking today: Challenges in Access and Sharing of Biospecimens

Friday 3rd December, 2021
10am - 1pm EST / 3pm - 6pm GMT

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How do we honor patients' rights and preferences while strengthening global secondary research with biospecimens and associated metadata?

Join us for an open forum discussion about the current global landscape for the access and sharing of biospecimens and associated metadata. How can we strengthen the biobanking system for ethical and sustainable advances in science and healthcare innovation?

What to expect:

The Open Forum will run online on Friday 3rd December, 2021,
from 10am - 1pm EST / 3pm - 6pm GMT.

FORUM AGENDA

Welcome and introduction

Following each one of the brief presentations, there will be time for questions and a discussion:

- **The patient perspective** on biospecimen and associated data - Dr. Jeff Allen, CEO Friends of Cancer Research
- The **value of biospecimen for secondary research** to advancing science for public health – Mr. Bill Leinweber, CEO National Disease Research Interchange

Brief Break

- The **international landscape** for use and sharing of biospecimens for secondary research - Dr. Zisis Kozlakidis, Head of Intern. Agency for Research on Cancer, WHO
- **Challenges with the sharing** of biospecimen and associated data - Dr. Simon Dowell, Head of Human Biological Sample Management, GSK

Brief Break

- The importance and mechanisms of **oversight: an academic perspective**- Dr. Jonathan Green, Dir. Office of Human Subjects Research Protection, NIH
- The importance and mechanisms of **oversight: a pharmaceutical industry**- Dr. Wohaib Hasan, Head of Biorepository Center, Takeda
- General discussion and close out

Facilitator: Dr Annette Schmid, Senior Director, Global Science Policy, Takeda.

Meet the Speakers:

The Biospecimens Open Forum speaker line-up includes:

Jeff Allen, PhD, Friends of Cancer Research (USA)

Jeff Allen is President and CEO of Friends of Cancer Research (Friends). For over 10 years, Jeff has been a driving force in the growth and success of the organization. Under his leadership, Friends has evolved into a nimble, forward-thinking policy, public affairs, and research organization. As President and CEO, he leads the strategic development and implementation of Friends' scientific, policy, research, and legislative initiatives, as well as overseeing Board governance and organizational operations. As a thought leader on many issues related to the Food and Drug Administration, regulatory strategy, and healthcare policy, he is regularly published in prestigious medical journals and policy publications.

Prior to joining Friends, Jeff was an endocrinology researcher at the National Institutes of Health. He received his Ph.D. in cell and molecular biology from Georgetown University, and holds a Bachelor's of Science in Biology from Bowling Green State University.

Simon Dowell, PhD, GlaxoSmithKline (UK)

Simon Dowell is the Head of Human Biological Sample Management for Pharma Research at GlaxoSmithKline. Through his career at the University of Oxford, Cancer Research UK and GSK he has specialised in the identification of novel drug targets and mechanisms, and he brings deep expertise in early-phase drug discovery.

In his current role, Simon is working to maximise the scientific opportunity of human biological samples in research, through simplifying the access to samples while maintaining the maximum respect for donors. He is passionate about cross-sector collaboration and developing unified strategies to tackle future global health challenges.

Jonathan M. Green, MD MBA, National Institutes of Health

Jonathan Green is Director, Office of Human Subjects Research Protections for the National Institutes of Health where he oversees the human research protection program for the NIH Intramural Research Program. Prior to joining the NIH, Dr Green was professor of medicine, pathology, and immunology, as well as Associate Dean for Human Studies, and Executive Chair of the institutional review board at Washington University School of Medicine in St. Louis, MO.

Dr. Green has had a long standing interest in biomedical ethics. He had been a member of the Barnes Jewish Hospital Ethics Committee since 2000, leading the clinical ethics consultation service from 2001-2005 and serving as Chair of the Ethics Committee from 2005-2009. After joining the Washington University Institutional Review Board in 2008, he assumed the role of committee co-chair in 2009. In 2010, he was appointed Associate Dean of Human Studies and Executive Chair of the IRB at Washington University in St Louis. Dr Green

served on the Secretaries Advisory Committee on Human Research Protections (SACHRP) from 2015-2018, also serving on the Subpart A subcommittee. Dr Green also currently serves on the Board of Directors for the Association for the Accreditation of Human Research Protection Programs (AAHRPP).

Wohaib Hasan, PhD, Biorepository Center Takeda (US)

Wohaib Hasan, PhD, is a neuroscientist by training. In his academic career as an Assistant Professor, Wohaib was awarded several US federal research awards investigating neuronal-endothelial imbalance in heart failure. As Biobank Officer at Takeda, Wohaib is spearheading efforts to put policies and procedures in place for secondary use of biospecimens collected as part of Takeda clinical trials.

Zisis Kozlakidis, PhD, World Health Organization (WHO)

Dr Zisis Kozlakidis is the Head of Laboratory Services and Biobanking at the International Agency for Research on Cancer, World Health Organization (IARC/WHO). He is responsible for one of the largest and most varied international collections of clinical samples in the world, focusing on gene–environment interactions and disease-based collections. This infrastructure supports multinational efforts in making treatments possible and delivering those to resource-restricted settings. Dr. Kozlakidis has significant expertise in the field of biobanking and has served as President of ISBER, and as MC member of BBMRI-ERIC.

Dr. Kozlakidis is a virologist, with a PhD in microbiology from Imperial College London. He is an elected Fellow of the Linnean Society of London, UK, and a Turnberg Fellow of the UK Academy of Medical Sciences. He serves as editor-in-Chief for scientific journal ‘Innovations in Digital Health, Diagnostics and Biomarkers’.

Bill Leinweber, MBA, National Disease Research Interchange (NDRI)

Bill Leinweber is President and CEO of National Disease Research Interchange, a world leader in the procurement, preservation and distribution of human tissue, cells and organs to support the advancement of biomedical research worldwide. He previously served as executive vice president of Research!America, a Washington, D.C.-based alliance of 400 member organizations dedicated to making medical and health research a higher national priority. He also was executive vice president of the American Academy of Physician Assistants (AAPA).

Bill received his MBA with honors from The Ohio State University and has completed post-graduate study at The Wharton School at the University of Pennsylvania. He is also a member of the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS).

Who should attend the Open Forum?

- Patients and patient organizations
- Scientists from academia and industry involved in research using human biospecimens
- Individuals from across the biospecimen and biobank industries
- Professionals, including ethicists, with an interest in the use of biospecimens for research

This forum is open and welcomes input from interested parties, including the general public, patients and patient advocacy organizations, colleagues from across the clinical trial spectrum, regulatory bodies and professional organizations.

We recognize this is largely affiliated to the USA and Europe, but a similar open forum is planned for Asia-Pacific in 2022.

Founding Members and Steering Committee

The group was founded with the coming together of individuals from academia, non-for profits, pharma, biotech and independent consultants with an interest in advancing Science Policy.

The Steering Committee, working on the Biospecimens Open Forum, currently includes (in alphabetical order):

Virginia Acha, DPhil Merck, Sharp and Dohme (UK)

Read more about Virginia on her [LinkedIn](#) profile

Barbara Bierer, MD, MRCT Brigham and Women's Hospital & Harvard University (US)

Read more about Barbara on her [LinkedIn](#) profile

Eleanor Dehoney, MSc, ResearchAmerica (USA)

Read more about Ellie via her [LinkedIn](#) page

Jon Fistein, MB BChir Private Healthcare Information Network (UK)

Read more about Jon on his [LinkedIn](#) profile

Shahid Hanif, PhD Avenzoar Consulting, (Canada)

You can read more about Shahid via [LinkedIn](#)

Wohaib Hasan, PhD, Takeda (USA)

Learn more about Wohaib here: [LinkedIn](#)

Namir Hassan, DPhil, Zelluna Immunotherapies (UK)

Read more about Namir on his [LinkedIn](#) profile

Mayumi Kusunose, MBE, MA, Riken Institute (Japan)

Read more about Mayumi on her [LinkedIn](#) profile

Gabriela Lavezzari, PhD, MBA, GSK (USA)

Find out more about Gabriela here: [LinkedIn](#)

Annette Schmid, PhD, Takeda (USA)

Read more about Annette here: [LinkedIn](#)

You can contact annette.schmid@takeda.com for further information.